

Blinded interpretation of face-mask study results

Discussion meeting 30th of May 2023

Timeline:

Date of the blinded assessment 30th of May 2023

Date of the document 30th of May 2023

Date of the updated document with supplementary interpretations 10th of June 2023

Date of planned publishing and unblinding 28th of June 2023

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The protocol and statistical analysis plan are published elsewhere [1]. We did not share any of the blinded results prior the discussion meeting. Petter Elstrøm conducted the analysis but did not know the true group allocation. The groups were labelled “0” and “1”. We recorded the meeting through Teams, and the recording will be published.

Interpretation on the primary outcome

In total, 3801 participants were included in the complete-case analysis, and 10.6% (n = 402) of the sample reported that they had experienced symptoms of respiratory tract infections during the trial. The analysis showed that the odds ratio on self-reported respiratory tract infections was significantly lower, with 95% CI not crossing 1, in favour participants allocated to one of the groups.

The group agreed that:

- The results indicated that the intervention of wearing face masks when close to others in public spaces over a period of 14 days had an effect – negative or positive.
- If the estimate of odds ratio favours the face masks group, our interpretation is that we have promising results that support our hypothesis, i.e., use of face masks in public can reduce the risk of getting respiratory tract infections.
- If the estimate of odds ratio favours the control group, our interpretation is that our intervention, i.e., use of face masks in public can increase the risk of respiratory tract infections, contrary to what we expect. If this is the actual results, we do not have sufficient information to fully explore and explain the findings beyond the pre-specified exploratory analysis.
- We acknowledge that self-reporting symptoms of respiratory tract infections has limitations, might be influenced by the group allocation and may be prone to bias.

The section below was written 10th of June 2023.

Some questions emerged after the meeting. These questions were related to multiple responses on the baseline form, mechanisms of missing data on primary outcome, and if the missing data on primary outcome could influence how we interpreted the results. These questions lead to discussions that included all authors, summarized below.

Multiple responses on the baseline form

After closer consideration and examination of the data, it became clear that most of the multiple responses were caused by errors related to the internet browser. Furthermore, most of the responses were identical to the first response, and only two participants were allocated to different groups. Hence, we agreed to include the participants using their first response and first group allocation.

Mechanisms of the missing data on primary outcome

At follow-up, 13% and 22% of participants in group 0 and 1, respectively, had missing data on the primary outcome. Having missing data in randomised controlled trials is not unusual, but we felt that the discrepancy of 9 percentage points needed to be discussed. We found little or no differences in baseline variables when comparing those with missing outcome data in group 0 and those with missing outcome data in group 1. The only variable that was significantly different between the groups were the usage of face masks two weeks prior to the intervention. This means that in one group, participants with missing data had more often reported using masks before randomization. This may indicate higher or lower susceptibility to infection in this group (higher, for example, if they wore masks due to higher exposure or due to higher personal risk, i.e., due to immunosuppression; lower, for example, if they wore masks due to higher risk awareness and overall, a stronger avoidance of exposure). We have no data to assess the likelihood of the various possible underlying mechanisms. We agreed that the discrepancy in missing data most likely is due to the group allocation. The authors discussed several potential hypotheses for the missing mechanism:

- If the group with 22% missing is the intervention group, we hypothesize that the larger proportion of missingness X (Figure 1) is caused by the allocation to wear face masks in public over 14 days. One plausible explanation is that the allocation entails an overall burden leading participants to not adhere with the intervention during the trial period, and consequently not respond on the follow-up questionnaire.
- If the group with 22% missing is the control group, the larger proportion of the missingness Y (Figure 1) might be caused by the allocation to not wear face masks in public over 14 days. We hypothesize that this allocation resulted in some participants not feeling that they have fully participated in the study, leading participants not to complete the trial, i.e., not

completing the end of study questionnaire (including reporting on symptoms of respiratory infection). However, participants who experienced respiratory symptoms during the study period may have been more prone to report this compared with those who did not experience such symptoms. This tendency may have been more pronounced in this (control) group than in the group wearing masks. Hence, the mechanism may influence the outcome detection and lead to an erroneous high infection rate among the “completed cases” in the control group. This again could lead to higher odds in the control group, but we have no data to support this mechanism.

- Overall, we failed to find a clearly plausible explanation to why the outcome would systematically influence participants’ tendency to complete the follow-up questionnaire. One hypothesis is that participants allocated to the intervention and who became sick during the trial, might not report that they were sick because they did not want the study to conclude that face masks do not help. The above-mentioned social desirability bias hypothesis can go in both directions, meaning that participants allocated to control, and who get sick, might not report that they were sick because they did not want the study to conclude that face masks help. The underlying mechanism to missingness remained uncertain with the data at hand.

In line with the analysis plan, the study group agreed to use multiple imputation by chained equations (MICE). We imputed data with 50 iterations using the prespecified variables sex, age, household size, number of children in the household, number of colleagues, attitude to face mask, use of face mask, use of public transport, and treatment allocation. We re-ran the same analysis presented in the meeting, using MICE, and the only difference between the two analyses was that the MICE-analysis included all participants allocated ($n = 4575$). The results of the MICE-analysis showed still a statistically significant difference between the two groups and the results were only marginally different from the complete-case analysis first presented. The interpretation of the findings remained unchanged from the meeting 30th of May.

Could missing data on primary outcome influence the interpretation of the main findings? To answer this question, Petter Elstrøm conducted two non-prespecified sensitivity analyses to assess how various levels of infection prevalence among participants with missing data could influence the main outcome. In the first sensitivity analysis, we estimated Manski bounds on treatment effect. This approach produces an interval estimate and a confidence interval on that interval by imputing the missing data to maximally favour and disfavour each treatment. Manski bounds are “sharp” in the sense that no other estimate of treatment effect is possible under the assumed analysis model and given the constraints imposed by the trial data. The second sensitivity

analysis considered more realistic scenarios using the mean score method suggested by White et al. [2] We made a matrix showing different levels of event proportion among the participants with missing data and how this influences the primary outcome in both groups. The event proportion among those with missing outcome data was varied up to 50% higher or down to 50% lower than the event proportion among completed cases in each group. We then discussed three different worst-case scenarios illustrated in figure 2:

- Scenario 1: the odds for infection in participants without outcome data in group 0 (i.e., the group with more complete data) is 50% lower than in completed cases in this group 0, and the odds among participants without outcome data in group 1 (i.e., the group with more missing data) is equal to the odds among completed cases in this group. This scenario corresponds to a setting where missing data in group 0 is positively correlated with being free of infections.
- Scenario 2: the odds for infection in participants without outcome data in group 1 is 50% higher than the odds among completed cases in this group, and the odds among participants without outcome data in group 0 is equal to the odds among completed cases in this group. This scenario corresponds to a setting where missing data in group 1 is positively correlated with having had an infection.
- Scenario 3: the odds for infection in participants without outcome data in group 0 is 50% lower than in completed cases in group 0, and the odds for infection in participants without outcome data in group 1 is 50% higher than in completed cases in group 1. This scenario corresponds to a setting where missing data is correlated with having had an infection in group 1 and not having had an infection in group 0.
- We did not assess the opposite scenario of “scenario 3” as this would represent a “best case scenario”, i.e., enhancing the difference between the groups.

We recreated datasets representing these scenarios and re-ran the main analysis on the primary outcome for each of the three scenarios. The results of these analyses, when compared to the main ITT analysis, were robust and only marginally different in scenario 1 and 2. In scenario 3, which is the most unlikely scenario of the three (representing a 50% decrease in the infection prevalence among missing in group 0 and at the same time a 50% increase in the infection prevalence among missing in group 1), the result was no longer statistically significant, with a 95% CI is slightly crossing 1. We concluded that missing data on the primary outcome does not influence the results substantially, and that our original blinded interpretation remained unchanged.

Figure 1 Trial flow including missing

Figure 2. Prevalence among missing change 0.05 unites from complete case at each step, up to 50% in each direction

Figure 3 Main analysis run on different scenarios of missing data primary outcome, including complete case, ITT and Manski's bounds

References

1. Solberg, R.B., Fretheim, Atle, Elgersma, Ingeborg H, Fagernes, Mette, Iversen, Bjørn G, Hemkens, Lars G, Rose, Christopher, & Elstrøm, Petter. , *Study protocol: The protective effect of face mask wearing against respiratory tract infections: a pragmatic randomized trial*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648390>. 2023.
2. White, I.R., J. Carpenter, and N.J. Horton, *A mean score method for sensitivity analysis to departures from the missing at random assumption in randomised trials*. *Stat Sin*, 2018. **28**(4): p. 1985-2003.